

ORAL CAVITY – A TOOL TO TRUTH

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THE EDGE

ABSTRACT

Forensic Odontology has been a subject of interest for dental aspirants who wish to broaden their scope of knowledge in the field of odontology. This educative passage, guided with a pictorial description helps in understanding how different areas of the oral cavity are of key importance in the field of forensics

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Forensic Odontology is a branch of dentistry that deals with the proper handling, examination and evaluation of dental evidence with the proper presentation of dental findings in the interest of justice.

The scope of oral cavity in forensic odontology is depicted in this image.

Brainstorm:

1. Is Forensic Odontology also called as Forensic Dentistry?
2. Do you know what is Cheiloscopy?
3. What is the study of Palatal Rugae called?

